

SOCIAL FACTORS IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Abstract

The primary goal of this work is to provide a detailed description of target language learners who are learning English as a foreign language and various social factors, such as age, gender, race, and ethnicity, which affect their language learning process.

Keywords: Sociolinguistics, age, gender, ethnicity, vernaculars, multilingualism, plurilingualism.

Introduction

Sociolinguistic Profile of a Group of Learners

Target group consists of 13 students. Seven of them are males, the rest are females. There are different age groups in the group including teenagers and young adults. Ten of them are Uzbek, two are Russian, and the one is Kazak. Their vernaculars are Uzbek, Russian, and Kazak respectively. According to Wardhaugh and Fuller (2014), vernacular refers to “the language a person grows up with and uses in everyday life in ordinary, commonplace, social interactions” (p. 28). Uzbek and Kazak students have mutual intelligibility among their vernaculars as they belong to one language family. Besides, these nations have lived together and socialized for a long time in near geographical space throughout the history. Almost all of my students are multilingual; according to Nuessel (2010), which refers to an individual who can use more than two languages depending on the social situation. My students know different languages such as Uzbek, Russian, Kazak, Turkish, and a bit of Arabic. Yet many of them are considered passive multilingual because they cannot produce utterances in L2, for example, in Russian. The Russian student is plurilingual since he acquired Uzbek by experiencing the Uzbek culture.

I chose the age and language background social factors as subgroups for my target learners. Since these factors are so essential to be taken account in my instructional context, I will be illustrating them in details below. Moreover, I covered other social factors like gender, race and ethnicity as these factors are so important in sociolinguistics and second language acquisition (SLA).

Age

As I have mentioned above, the group consists of two different age groups: teenagers and adults. I will provide details in a table so that it is easy to show:

N	Age groups	Male	Female
1	Teenagers	2 (17-18)	3 (16-17)
2	Adults	5 (22-25)	3 (21-26)

Table 1

There are two different age groups in my target classroom: teenagers and adults. The teenager group consists of two male students, aged 17 and 18, and three female students, aged

16 and 17. There are five males who are between 22 and 25; and three females who are between 21 and 26 in the adult group (*Table 1*). Wardhaugh and Fuller (2014) included age-grading phenomenon as an example of the influence of social organization of age groups on the language spoken in these groups. According to this phenomenon, young people speak differently from older people and vice versa. This can be observed in English usage among my students, their choice of grammar, lexical items and styles can vary depending on their age.

Language Background

My target group of learners is good at learning languages. The majority of them have good and rich language background which should be beneficial for learning English. They are well-aware of the standardized form of their first language which enables them to learn other languages effectively and efficiently by comparing and contrasting. In addition, some female students acquired the Turkish language by watching movies. As they said, the exposure to target language and the high level of intrinsic motivation helped them to improve their Turkish. The Russian student also picked up Uzbek in his neighborhood when he played with his peers in his childhood.

However, when it comes to the English language, almost all of them studied it by attending tutorial classes. According to the needs analysis I conducted with the group, they all learned English at school, lyceum or other higher education to some extent. As they reported in the needs analysis, they forgot most of the things they learned in their mandatory education. Another significant point about their English I should mention is that their vernaculars considerably impact their ideolects in English, which is considered an individual way of speaking, including sounds, words, grammar, and style, according to Wardhaugh and Fuller (2014).

Social Factors

Gender

The topic of gender is relevant in my instructional setting and should be taken into account while teaching as language use and gender are interlinked with each other. The way males and females speak differ from one another in several ways. According to Mesthrie et al. (2009), linguistic distinctions between males and females are seen as indexical of social practices and beliefs, which means language plays a role as a social mirror to reflect social distinctions. According to the various research findings provided by Mesthrie et al. (2009), general idea about men's and female's language is that women are more likely to use prestige language; while men tend to use more vernacular language in conversations.

Moreover, the empirical study carried out among English speakers in western context demonstrates the distinctions in male and female speeches according to the amount of talk, interruptions, conversational support, tentativeness, and compliments. The result showed that males speak more than females, especially in formal and public context, and they interrupt women more than vice versa. The rest three categories were more common among female speakers; they tend to support their partners by short phrases, keep their speech hesitant and tentative by using hedges, and make more compliments. These categories are applicable for my target learners as well. From my observations, my male students try to be dominant in conversations and debates we organize; whereas the female students tend to be cooperative and tentative in their speeches. They try not to hurt others when they speak. In addition, my male students are keen to learn informal language; they usually bring different jargons and

slangs taken from songs and media. On the other hand, my female students prefer to learn Standard English and use prestige form of English. So, relying on these arguments, gender is important and relevant topic in my instructional context.

Race

The topic of race is not common in my country as it is in other parts of the world. It is not relevant topic for my instructional setting. One of the reasons can be that people have not been treated according to their race throughout the history in Uzbekistan. Also, it is not common social factor in education and other fields. Rather, people are usually treated depending on where they come from. People who are from regions or rural areas might be discriminated in certain context. In education, student might also be categorized and addressed according to their hometowns. Yet, it is not essential social factor in my teaching context.

Ethnicity

Fought (2011) included that ethnicity is strongly bonded with language. Researchers seem to agree that ethnicity cannot be understood itself as isolated from other social factors such as social class, age, and gender (Fought, 2011, p. 240). As ethnicity is central and connected with other social variables in sociolinguistics, it is definitely relevant and worth considering in my teaching context as well. Also, both of the subgroups I chose to describe my target learners were demonstrated in details as social variables in connection with ethnicity by the same author. The way students speak, the way they choose language forms, the way they choose style and register, these all reflect their ethnic identity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is clear that various social factors such as age, gender, and ethnicity play crucial roles in shaping the language learning process of my target learners. The sociolinguistic profile of this group highlights the diversity in their language backgrounds, their multilingual abilities, and the impact of their vernaculars on their English learning journey. Age is a significant factor in how they engage with the language, as younger learners tend to have different linguistic preferences compared to adults. Gender, too, influences their communication styles, with male and female learners showing distinct approaches to language use. Although race is not a major factor in my context, ethnicity plays a key role, as it is interconnected with their identity and language choices. Understanding these factors helps me tailor my teaching methods to meet the specific needs of my learners, making the language learning experience more effective and meaningful. By acknowledging the social dynamics within the classroom, I can foster a learning environment that utilizes these differences to promote better learning outcomes.

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